

PREPARING FUTURE PRESCHOOL TEACHERS TO IMPROVE HEALTH-PRESERVING KNOWLEDGE IN THE FORMATION OF CULTURAL AND HYGIENIC SKILLS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. *This article discusses the need to increase health-preserving knowledge for the formation of cultural and hygienic skills in preschool children through effective interaction in the “teacher-doctor-parent” system.*

Keywords: *health care, knowledge, cultural and hygienic skills, interactions, student, educator, doctor, parent.*

The problem of preserving and strengthening the health of the younger generation remains relevant for all countries. Currently, one of the most important and global problems of states is the health of children, constituting one of the priority areas not only of educational and medical institutions, but also of the entire society as a whole, since only healthy children are able to properly engage in various types of activities, learn, and development.

Raising a healthy child and ensuring the safety of his life is what parents, educators and teachers of educational organizations at all levels of the continuing education system need to do today.

In this regard, an important mission of modern preschool education in Uzbekistan is to instill in children the need to lead a healthy lifestyle, to develop an understanding of the need to be active in preserving and strengthening their health and the health of others.

At the present stage of development of society, the policy of our state is that today the country needs not only highly qualified specialists, but also, above all, highly educated young people, formed as individuals who have learned the inexhaustible values accumulated by humanity in this area, deeply aware that in a legal, democratic society, people must be independent thinkers, capable of making informed decisions to preserve and strengthen their health and the population as a whole.

The problem of preserving and purposefully developing children’s health in modern conditions remains a priority state task. Over the past period, large-scale work has been carried out in the country to organize an effective preschool education system, designed to ensure the formation of a healthy and comprehensively developed younger generation, the introduction of effective forms and methods of health-saving education and upbringing into the educational process.

This problem to a certain extent serves the implementation of the tasks formulated in the resolutions and Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan: dated September 30, 2018 No. PD-3955 “On measures to improve the management system of preschool education, on the approval of the Concept for the development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 [1], Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Preschool Education and Upbringing”, Tashkent, December 14, 2019 [2]. Resolution of the President of the Republic of

Uzbekistan “On additional measures to improve the system for protecting children’s rights”, Tashkent, May 29, 2020 [3]. State curriculum of preschool educational institution “First step” Tashkent 2018 [4]. State requirements for the development of children of early and preschool age of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent 2018 (updated in 2022) [5].

In Uzbekistan, issues of health conservation are discussed in the works of D.D.Sharipova, M.Tairova [6], T.S.Muhammadiyeva and etc. [7].

A review of scientific research by domestic and foreign authors indicates that to this day the issues of forming a healthy lifestyle and health culture have been considered in some detail, theoretical provisions have been developed on the philosophy of health of children and adolescents, but in these studies the problem of improving the methodology for forming initial ideas about health protection and life safety by future teachers of pupils of preschool educational organizations.

Educational activities within the framework of traditional health and preventive measures to this day do not go beyond the level of informing the population. The focus on mechanical reproduction of knowledge leads to ineffective human perception of the information provided. The formation of behavior in the course of solving goals and objectives (algorithmic steps) in the implementation of programs for the formation of a healthy lifestyle has not yet been clearly formulated, which makes their effective implementation difficult. Expanding the educational space also involves expanding the arsenal of tools and methods that a modern specialist in developing health-preserving knowledge should have at his disposal [8].

It is possible to successfully influence the state of a child’s health only if parents and specialists (teachers of preschool educational organizations, doctors, psychologists) understand that personal health is a means for self-expression and self-improvement, success and quality of life of a person. The health and future professional activity of each child are interconnected and interdependent, since the stronger a person’s health, the more productive his work and the possibility of psycho-social adaptation in the process of personality formation [9].

We conducted research on the availability of health-saving knowledge among students of preschool pedagogical universities - future teachers of preschool educational institutions, to study the level of knowledge about the concepts of “health-saving”, about the need to develop “health-saving competence” of teachers, about knowledge of health-saving methods and techniques, as well as knowledge of the main components healthy lifestyle, etc. As a result, it was revealed that the level of knowledge on these issues at the beginning of the experimental study ranged from 18.8 to 22%.

During the ascertaining experiment, we tried to find out the students’ opinion about whether they know about the tasks of health-saving activities reflected in the State requirements and in the “Ilk Kadam” program. The majority of students gave positive answers, but only 17% sufficiently named the basic health-preserving competencies that need to be developed in preschool children.

Students were asked to rank, that is, determine the place in order of importance, which approaches should be improved when organizing health conservation in preschool educational institutions. Student responses were presented in the form of 11 approaches in order of importance and relevance to the educational process. According to students, the most important and relevant for the proper organization of the educational process is: nutrition - 64 respondents (13.4%), in second place is the organization of motor activity - 49 respondents (10.2%), in third place is the

education of a responsible and caring attitude to their health - 46 respondents (9.6%), in fourth place was the psycho-emotional comfort of the participants - 40 respondents (8.4%), 5th and 6th places were taken by hardening and introducing innovations in the field of physical education of preschool children - 39 respondents (8.2%). 7th and 8th places were allocated to such issues as medical care and education of a hygienic culture - 35 people (7.3%), compliance with the motor regime was in 9th place - 33 (6.9%) respondents, advanced training was named in 10th place personnel - 31 people (6.5%), 11 approach - working with the family, 30 (6.3%) respondents and finally, 37 people (7.7%) - did not give an answer.

In working with students, special attention was paid to the implementation of the problem of interaction between all persons involved in the formation of health-preserving knowledge and cultural and hygienic skills, i.e. teachers, medical workers and parents to implement this problem. In our opinion, the formation of cultural and hygienic skills in preschool children is ensured by the organization of effective interaction in the “teacher-doctor-child-parent” system and includes:

- strengthening the orientation of the activities of teachers and parents towards a healthy lifestyle;

- replenishment of health-saving theoretical knowledge of both teachers and parents, mastery of health systems and technologies, acquisition and consolidation of practical skills of a healthy lifestyle, active participation in health-improving activities;

- formation in preschool children of adequate ideas about their own body, and about the factors influencing human health and its safety;

- instilling in children basic cultural and hygienic skills that transform into healthy habits.

From habit to need, from need to a healthy lifestyle, this should be the algorithm for the activities of preschool educational institutions [10].

The pedagogical experiment we conducted, aimed at increasing the effectiveness of acquired health-preserving knowledge and life safety, made it possible to scientifically substantiate the methodology for increasing this knowledge, the ways of its application, as well as to substantiate the forms and methods for the interaction of teachers, educators, doctors and parents in working with children in preschool educational institutions.

REFERENCES

1. Постановление Президента Республики Узбекистан «О мерах по дальнейшему совершенствованию системы дошкольного образования» от 30 сентября 2018 года №ПП-3955.
2. Закона Республики Узбекистан «О дошкольном образовании и воспитании» г.Ташкент, 14 декабря 2019 г.
3. Постановлении Президента Республики Узбекистан «О дополнительных мерах по совершенствованию системы защиты прав ребенка» г.Ташкент 29 мая 2020 г.
4. Государственная учебная программа дошкольного образовательного учреждения «Илк кадам». Ташкент.- 2018.
5. Государственные требования к развитию детей раннего и дошкольного возраста Республики Узбекистан. Ташкент.- 2018.
6. Шарипова Д.Д., Таирова М.Т., Каримова С. Здоровьесберегающая деятельность педагога в образовательном процессе. Образование и здоровье: Сб.матер

- Всероссийской науч. шк.здоровья с мкждународным участием, 19-21 марта 2013, Стерлитамак: СФ БашГУ, 2013, 201-204 с.
7. Шарипова Д.Д., Мухаммадиева С. Профессиональная подготовка специалистов по дошкольному воспитанию, ориентированных на реализацию гигиенического воспитания. Т., Ж.Педагогик таълими, №1, 2004.
 8. Белостоцкая Е.М., Виноградова Т.Ф. и др. Гигиенические основы воспитания детей от 3 до 7. – М.: Просвещение, 1991.
 9. Урунтаева Г.А., Афонькина Ю.А. Как приобщить малыша к гигиене и самообслуживанию. – М.: Просвещение, 1997.
 10. Сайфиева С.С. Повышение здоровьесберегающих знаний детей дошкольного возраста. Педагогические науки №2, 2012.